

**ORGANIZATION OF INTENSIVE GARDENS HIGH INCOME THE FOUNDATION OF
OBTAINING**

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Annotation: *this article mainly describes the importance of intensive Gardens today, the agrotechnics of garden construction. At the same time, the article also describes the advantages and disadvantages of intensive Gardens. Information is also provided on what irrigation methods are used along with the formation of intensive Gardens.*

Keywords: *intensive, garden, water, resource, drip irrigation, simbagaz, agriculture, ecology, agrotechnics, global, tree.*

Today there is a period when a huge number of environmental problems are raging in the world. Due to environmental problems, various natural problems are in full swing today, which is why it is not losing its influence on both agriculture and of course. Today, agriculture is mainly affected by problems such as global warming, increased demand for Water Resources, various damage to the crop caused by kunanda, various levels of excessive salinity of the lands, erosion of fertile soils, in addition to various problems, agriculture is affected by this, the main reason is a violation of Ecology, and environmental degradation is the excessive and inefficient use of Natural Resources On the territory of Uzbekistan, too, the yield level of some annual crop species is decreasing due to various factors, and to prevent this, it would be advisable not to occupy land with one type of crop, but to establish gardens and vines on soils with a relatively low yield. For this reason, it will also be advisable to shape new gardens albata. If we dwell on the intensive garden grid, which today has a high efficiency, then the cooling of the fruit has been completely eliminated by the use of advanced agrotechnical measures in modern intensive Gardens. The yield is also considered 1.5-1.7 times higher than that of previous intensive Gardens. Alternatively, the fruit of today's intensive Gardens is an export bop product in addition to the fact that in the conditions of Uzbekistan, such gardens become a source of net income for several years, covering the expenses spent at most in 3-5 years, have also been tried in experiments. If we dwell on the requirements for the organization of intensive gardens, it should be noted that in the land where low and desolate gardens are planted, fresh groundwater should not be close to 1.5-2 M and mineralized groundwater should not be close to 3-3.5 m. And in the land near the rivers, the groundwater level will be 1.0-1.2 m. only their soil composition should be free of harmful (chloride and sulfate) salts. The area allocated for irrigated intensive gardens should be flat and its slope should not exceed 4-5 degrees. The fruit tree grown in simbagazy gardens should be 100 cm wide in mature trees and 150 cm in low-lying trees so that the sun illuminates the trunk well in addition to the fact that when the rows are 3.5-4.0 m between the trees their bodies will be well provided with sunlight. Every year, potassium 60-70 kg of nitrogen fertilizers are applied per hectare in the fall, with a volume of 40-50 kg of phosphorus 30-40 kg, until the fruit trees are fully harvested. In addition to different times, different types of drugs are used for the purpose of making hioia from kunanda. One of the most convenient aspects of intensive Gardens is that in this type of gardens, it is very convenient to apply modern types of irrigation, in particular drip irrigation, and allows you to achieve high efficiency. In addition, it is possible to plant pulses between the trees, which indicates additional income. Let's dwell on the advantages of creating intensive Gardens in an additional way: The fact that the yield level is high, it quickly covers the costs incurred, it is easy to apply agrotechnical work, its yield is high-quality (exportbop is a product), the length of storage of crop from gardens, the creation of workplaces when processing enterprises are built, the saving of irrigation water when modern irrigation methods are used, etc. One of the reasons why much attention has been paid to the creation of long-term Gardens in the Republic to date is the fact that it is very convenient to export the crop from deer to foreign countries. Higher yields can be achieved each year if agrotechnical work is weather - permeable in time, unlike annuals because crops from gardens and vines are perennial. Just as everything has an advantage, intensive gardens also have disadvantages that include those below: Creating intensive Gardens requires investment: Failure to give the intended yield

if agratechnics are not followed; Examples include the fact that varieties brought from abroad can hit cold in winter, and in summer they suffer from various diseases, etc.

Although there are some shortcomings in the organization of intensive gardens, but the organization of intensive Gardens is considered promising plans. For this reason, crop varieties suitable for our new natural conditions are being tested on yartilib test sites by Uzbek scientists. In conclusion, foreign countries are considered to have extensive experience in creating intensive Gardens. This is another great achievement for us if we can apply it to ourselves by studying the experiences of foreign countries. For this reason, much attention is paid to improving personnel skills today. Personnel qualification increases are a pledge of future achievements.

LIST OF LITERATURE USED:

1. Khamidov, M. K., Juraev, U. A., Buriev, X. B., Juraev, A. K., Saksonov, U. S., Sharifov, F. K., & Isabaev, K. T. (2023, February). Efficiency of drip irrigation technology of cotton in saline soils of Bukhara oasis. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1138, No. 1, p. 012007). IOP Publishing.
2. Sharifov Firdavs, & Mirzamurotov Mirshod. (2024). G'O'ZA O'SIMLIGINI YETISHTIRISHDA SUV TEJAMKOR SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASH. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 461–464. Retrieved from <https://uzconference.com/index.php/p/article/view/98>
3. Sattorovich, S. U., & Qobil o'g'li, S. F. (2022). BUG 'DOY O 'SIMLIGI VA DONINING XALQ XO 'JALIGIDA BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI.
4. Xamrayev Kamol, Sharifov Firdavs, & Yusupova Oynura. (2024). TUPROQ SHO'RINI YUVISHDA BIOSOLVENT BIRIKMASINI TUPROQ SUV-TUZ MUVOZANATIGA TA'SIRI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 458–460. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/97>
5. Nurov, D. E. (2014). APPLICATION OF DRIP IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGY FOR COTTON GROWING IN CONDITIONS OF WATER SHORTAGE. The Way of Science, 24.
6. Нуров, Д. Э. (2020). ВАЖНОСТЬ И ПЕРСПЕКТИВЫ КАПЕЛЬНОГО ОРОШЕНИЯ. Экономика и социум, (11 (78)), 1064-1067.
7. Саримсаков, М. М. (2023, May). СПОСОБЫ ПОЛИВА И УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ ИНТЕНСИВНЫХ ЯБЛОНЕВЫХ САДОВ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 14, pp. 173-175).
8. Shaxrilloevich, I. I. (2023). DIDACTIC CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF STUDENTS OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH. Academia Repository, 4(10), 142-145.
9. Шахриллович И (2021). Педагогические условия формирования готовности выпускников вузов к трудоустройству. ACADEMICIA: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ МНОГОДИСЦИПЛИНАРНЫЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ , 11 (1), 881-884.
10. Khamidov, M., & Khamraev, K. (2023). Modern salinity leaching technology of agricultural land reclamation (A case study from Bukhara region, Uzbekistan). In E3S Web of Conferences (Vol. 410, p. 05008). EDP Sciences.
11. BOBIROVA, M. B., KADIROV, Z. Z., & KHAMRAEV, K. S. (2021). IMPROVEMENT OF IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR SOYBEAN GROWTH. In Поколение будущего: Взгляд молодых ученых-2021 (pp. 247-250).
12. Shavkat o'g'li, E. S., & Sirojiddin o'g'li, S. J. (2023). TRANSITION TO MODERN WATER-SAVING IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES-THE NEED OF THE TIME. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 332-339
13. Shaxboz, E. (2023). ZAMONAVIY SUV TEJAMKOR SUGORISH TEXNOLOGIYALARIGA OTISH-ZAMON TALABI. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 414-419)
14. Sharifov Firdavs, & Mirzamurotov Mirshod. (2024). G'O'ZA O'SIMLIGINI YETISHTIRISHDA SUV TEJAMKOR SUG'ORISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASH. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 461–464. Retrieved from <https://uzconference.com/index.php/p/article/view/98>
15. Khamidov, M. K., Juraev, U. A., Buriev, X. B., Juraev, A. K., Saksonov, U. S., Sharifov, F. K., & Isabaev, K. T. (2023, February). Efficiency of drip irrigation technology of cotton in saline soils of Bukhara oasis. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1138, No. 1, p. 012007). IOP Publishing.
16. Худайев, И., & Тожиев, Ш. (2023). БОФ ВА УЗУМЗОРЛАРДА ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИНИ ЖОРИЙ ҚИЛИШНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ. Talqin va

Tadqiqotlar, 1(1). извлечено от

17. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2023, October). ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИ ОРҚАЛИ СУҒОРИЛГАН ОЛМА БОҒЛАРИНИНГ ТУПРОҚ АГРОКИМЁВИЙ КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИ. In Proceedings of International Conference on Educational Discoveries and Humanities (Vol. 2, No. 11, pp. 19-23).
18. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2019). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. ЖУРНАЛ АГРО ПРОЦЕССИНГ, (4).
19. Xudayev, I. J., & Tojiyev, S. M. (2023). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKLANLI EGATLARDAN G‘O‘ZANI SUG‘ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. In Uz-Conferences (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 514-519).
20. Худайев, И., & Фазлиев, Ж. ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ КАПЕЛЬНОГО ОРОШЕНИЯ САДОВ И ВИНОГРАДНИКОВ. JURNALI, 176
21. Fazliyev, J. (2017). Drip irrigation technology in gardens. Интернаука. Science Journal, 7(11).
22. Fazliyev, J. (2018). Modern irrigation methods for gardens. Science, 22, 24-26.
23. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш., & Баратов, С. С. (2014). ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТЬ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ГЛИНИСТОЙ ВОДЫ ПРИ КАПЕЛЬНОМ ОРОШЕНИИ. The Way of Science, (4), 77.
24. Fazliyev, J. EFFICIENCY OF APPLYING THE WATER-SAVING IRRIGATION TECHNOLOGIES IN IRRIGATED FARMING «ИНТЕРНАУКА» Science Journal № 21 (103) June 2019 г.
25. Khudaev, I., & Fazliev, J. (2022). Water-saving irrigation technology in the foothill areas in the south of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Современные инновации, системы и технологии, 2(2), 0301-0309
26. Фазлиев, Ж. Ш. (2017). Боғларда томчилатиб суғориш технологияси. Интернаука, (7-3), 71-73.
27. Худайев , И., & Тожиев , Ш. (2023). БОҒ ВА УЗЎМЗОРЛАРДА ТОМЧИЛАТИБ СУҒОРИШ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯСИНИ ЖОРИЙ ҚИЛИШНИНГ САМАРАДОРЛИГИ. Talqin Va Tadqiqotlar, 1(1). извлечено от <https://talqinvatadqiqotlar.uz/index.php/tvt/article/view/220>
28. Фазлиев Жамолiddин, Тожиев Шерзод, & Холиқов Шарифбек. (2024). СПОСОБЫ ЭКОНОМИИ ВОДНЫХ РЕСУРСОВ В САДАХ. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 520–525. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/110>
29. J.Sh.Fazliyev., Sh.M.Tojiyev., Sh.D.Khalikov. (2024). EFFICIENCY OF USE OF CLAY WATER WITH DROP IRRIGATION. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 504–509. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/107>.
30. I.J.Xudayev, I.J.Xudayev, & Sh.M.Tojiyev. (2024). NAMLATGICH-BLOKLARDAN HOSIL QILINGAN EKLANLI EGATLARDAN G‘O‘ZANI SUG‘ORISH TEXNOLOGIYASI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 514–519. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/109>
31. Khamidov, M. K., Juraev, U. A., Buriev, X. B., Juraev, A. K., Saksonov, U. S., Sharifov, F. K., & Isabaev, K. T. (2023, February). Efficiency of drip irrigation technology of cotton in saline soils of Bukhara oasis. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science (Vol. 1138, No. 1, p. 012007). IOP Publishing.
32. Sharifov Firdavs, & Mirzamurotov Mirshod. (2024). G‘O‘ZA O‘SIMLIGINI YETISHTIRISHDA SUV TEJAMKOR SUG‘ORISH TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO‘LLASH. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 461–464. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/98>
33. Sattorovich, S. U., & Qobil o‘g‘li, S. F. (2022). BUG ‘DOY O ‘SIMLIGI VA DONINING XALQ XO ‘JALIGIDA BUGUNGI KUNDAGI AHAMIYATI.
34. Xamrayev Kamol, Sharifov Firdavs, & Yusupova Oynura. (2024). TUPROQ SHO‘RINI YUVISHDA BIOSOLVENT BIRIKMASINI TUPROQ SUV-TUZ MUVOZANATIGA TA‘SIRI. Uz-Conferences, 1(1), 458–460. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/97>
35. Shodiev, Z. O., Inoyatov, I. S., & Shodiev, N. S. (2020). NATURAL PASTE AND ITS VALUE TODAY. In *Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве* (pp. 198-200).
36. Shaxrilloevich, I. I. (2023). DIDACTIC CONDITIONS FOR THE PREPARATION OF STUDENTS OF VOCATIONAL EDUCATION FOR PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY BASED ON AN INNOVATIVE APPROACH. *Academia Repository*, 4(10), 142-145.

37. Шахриллоевич П (2021). Педагогические условия формирования готовности выпускников вузов к трудоустройству. *ACADEMICIA: МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ МНОГОДИСЦИПЛИНАРНЫЙ ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКИЙ ЖУРНАЛ*, 11 (1), 881-884.
38. Ochilovich, S. Z. (2020, September). Inoyatov Ikrom Shaxriloyevich, Shodiyev Ne'matjon Sadirovich. Tabiiy uyulovlar va uning bugungi kundagi ahamiyati. In *Эффективность применение инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве» международная научно-практическая онлайн-конференция* (pp. 25-26).
39. Ikrom, I. (2023). KASBIY TAYYORGARLIKNING RIVOJLANISH DINAMIKASI BO'YICHA PEDAGOGIK TAJRIBA-SINOV ISHLARI NATIJALARINING TAHLILI. In *Uz-Conferences* (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 626-633).
40. EUsarov, J., JEsnaev, N., OKhakov, J., ISaidova, D., ShInoyatov, I., & SShodiev, N. (2022). THE SOCIAL SIGNIFICANCE OF CREATING A MECHANISM OF PSYCHOLOGICAL STUDY OF THE CHILDRENS SPIRIT IN CRISIS FAMILIES. *NeuroQuantology*, 20(16), 4614.
41. Musinovich, S. M. (2023, June). DRIP IRRIGATION INTENSIVE APPLE ORCHARDS AND SEASONAL WATER CONSUMPTION. In *Proceedings of Scientific Conference on Multidisciplinary Studies* (Vol. 2, No. 6, pp. 8-14).
42. Саримсаков, М. М. (2023, May). СПОСОБЫ ПОЛИВА И УРОЖАЙНОСТЬ ИНТЕНСИВНЫХ ЯБЛОНЕВЫХ САДОВ. In *INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE* (Vol. 2, No. 14, pp. 173-175).
43. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). USE OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR PROJECT-CONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY. *Экономика и социум*, (10-2 (101)), 167-169.
44. Sadirovich, S. N. (2022). The Significance of Problem Situation Assignments in Teaching the Science of Machine Details. *Central Asian Journal of Theoretical and Applied Science*, 3(8), 30-32.
45. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). KINEMATIC STUDY OF FLAT BASE MECHANISMS. *E Conference Zone*, 61-69. Retrieved from <https://www.econferencezone.org/index.php/ecz/article/view/888>
46. Shodiyev Ziyodullo Ochilovich, & Shodiyev Nematjon Sadirovich. (2022). STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON THE DRYING PROCESS OF COTTON RAW MATERIALS. *Conferencea*, 47-50. Retrieved from <https://conferencea.org/index.php/conferences/article/view/295>
47. Shodiev, N. S. (2022). " PREPARING ENGINEERING STUDENTS FOR DESIGNCONSTRUCTION ACTIVITY THROUGH TEACHING" MACHINE DETAILS". *International Journal of Early Childhood Special Education*, 14(7).
48. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abduganievich, D. N., Nematovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). EFFECT OF FORCES ON AIR CONVEYING DEVICES AND NETWORK ON COTTON SEED QUALITY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 771-775.
49. Nematovich, S. S., Abduganievich, D. N., & Sadirovich, S. N. (2021). TECHNOLOGY OF PRODUCTION OF CERAMIC MATERIALS AND ITS VALUE TODAY. *Galaxy International Interdisciplinary Research Journal*, 9(12), 768-770.
50. Ochilovich, S. Z., Abdug'aniyevich, D. N., Ne'matovich, S. S., & Sadirovich, S. N. M. (2021). Methods Of Kinematic Study of Flat Base Mechanisms. *Texas Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*, 3, 208-214.
51. Садир Нематович Шодиев1, Неъматжон Садирович Шодиев2. (2024). ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЙ АНАЛИЗ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЗАБИВАЕМОСТИ ТРУБОК РАДИАТОРА НА ТЕПЛОВОЕ СОСТОЯНИЯ ДВИГАТЕЛЯ. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 145-151. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/32>
52. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). INTEGRATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI O'QITISHNING ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALARI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 945-950. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/195>
53. Shodiyev Ne'matjon. (2024). TEXNIKA OLIY TA'LIM MUASSASALARIDA UMUMKASBIY FANLARNI AXBOROT TA'LIM MUHITIDA O'QITISHNING MUHIM YO'NALISHLARI. *Uz-Conferences*, 1(1), 938-944. Retrieved from <https://uz-conference.com/index.php/p/article/view/194>